

STUDY TITLE: Mapping the Emergency Medicine Landscape in Tanzania: A Workforce and Health Facility Study Fifteen Years After Its Introduction

Appendix 1: Data Collection Tool :Healthcare Workforce Questionnaire

1. Full name of physician
 - a. Has met all inclusion criteria (tick)
 - b. Has NOT met any of the exclusion criteria (tick)
2. Year of Birth
3. Year of graduation
4. Nationality
5. Country of Training
 - a. Tanzania (MUHAS)
 - b. Outside Tanzania (Mention country)_____
6. Current primary region of practice
 - a. In Tanzania (mention region/scroll down)
 - b. Outside Tanzania (Africa) – mention
 - c. Outside Tanzania (Europe, USA, Asia) – mention
7. For those in Tanzania, Facility is in
 - a. Rural
 - b. Urban
 - c. Semi Urban
8. Current role
 - a. Clinical
 - b. Non-Clinical (administrative, faculty-only, policy, research)
 - c. Mixed (Clinical and non-clinical)
9. Type of Facility EMP affiliated with (for those with clinical role)
 - a. Public
 - b. Private
 - c. Faith based organization/NGO
 - d. Others (mention)

10. Level of affiliated institute (for those with clinical role)

- a. Dispensary
- b. Health Center
- c. District Hospital
- d. Regional Referral Hospital
- e. Zonal Hospital
- f. National Hospital

11. Institute affiliated with (Nonclinical role) - mention